

D5.3 National Meetings Reports 2012

Revision: Final

Editors: Susan Schreibman and Vicky Garnett (TCD)

Contributors: Stefan Strathmann and Claudia Engelhardt (UGOE)
Ann Gow and Laura Molloy (HATII)
Jurate Kupriene (VUL)
Chiara Cirinná, (FRD)

Executive Summary

In 2012, DigCurV Partners organised or attended National Meetings for the express purpose of promoting the activities of DigCurV and the Curriculum Framework development.

At each meeting, the rationale behind the lenses was discussed, and the uses of lenses themselves were explained

Many partners used the meetings as a means to promote DigCurV. UGOE suggest that their meeting ‘...served as a platform for the exchange of experiences...’ and highlighted how useful the meeting was for networking. Other partners found other useful feedback from the meetings, particularly with regards to promoting future events, discussing the Curriculum Framework in its current form, and using the CURATE! game as a means of raising topics for discussion.

This report looks at each national meeting in turn by country of the reporting partner. Details of the reports are presented in sections looking at the audience profile of the event, the outcomes of the meetings, and the impact of the meeting.

The report concludes with a summary of the feedback and information taken from each meeting, and present recommendations for future meetings and work of the network.

Feedback gathered

The partners reported receiving positive feedback on the development of the Curriculum Framework, with suggestions for its further development. VUL, for example, indicated that users would like to see further expansion of the descriptors within the framework, a notion that was also expressed by the participants of UGOE’s evaluation workshop who discussed the framework within the context of qualification.

Use of CURATE!

The DigCurV game, CURATE! was used by UGOE, TCD and VUL during their National Meetings as either a means of engaging and drawing participants in to discuss the work of DigCurV, or as a means to 'lightly' discuss the issues previously raised during earlier presentations on the day. The success of the game can clearly be seen, even though it has only been in development over the past year. Further use and indeed development of the game should be investigated as this has become one of the projects biggest means of dissemination.

Promotion of the DigCurV 'mission'

All partners saw the National Meetings as an opportunity to bring the work of the DigCurV project to a wider audience. In some cases (UGOE, TCD and HATII) the meeting was held in conjunction with partners, some of whom are more prominent in their respective countries than DigCurV would be. By teaming up with these larger organisations, DigCurV was able to showcase the Curriculum Framework, and the mission of the project as a whole to this already captivated audience. Feedback in this regard came through numbers of materials distributed during the event, comments and request for information from the relevant DigCurV partner either during or immediately after the event or, in the case of FRD, through an increased interest in taking part in future DigCurV events, such as the Final Conference in May 2013.

Recommendations and future work

The reports from the partners all show that the name and work of DigCurV has been brought to a wider audience as a result of these meetings. Many with professional and personal interest in Digital Curation and Preservation techniques and training, from libraries to broadcast media archives, engaged with the DigCurV partners and either gave feedback on the current work, or expressed an interest in seeing where the project goes from here.

This feedback and interest indicates that the Curriculum Framework could be used in multiple circumstances; for individual professional development, or for recruitment of individuals. In terms of further development for the project, the responses seem to express a desire for an expanded version of the framework.

Use of the CURATE! game during these types of events is a useful tool for getting participants to discuss the issues at hand in an entertaining way, rather than through the standard formal presentation format. DigCurV therefore intends to use the game during the Final Conference in May.

Furthermore, as the CURATE! game has proved so popular, further development would be a great step for the DigCurV project, particularly as the issues raised within the game complement the Curriculum Framework so neatly.